

Accreditation of Specialties Across Departments for Postgraduate Medical Training at the Rivers State University Teaching Hospital

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More Information

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Abstract

Background: Accreditation, a determination of institutional “fitness” for training, is a tasking exercise requiring participation of trainers, staff, learners, and the commitment of the administration. This study therefore evaluated the accreditation of specialty training programs across the Departments at the Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, focusing on the visits and outcome of visits by the accrediting colleges in the year 2024.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was carried out among Heads of Departments (HODs) using a semi-structured self-administered questionnaire. Data obtained was analysed and presented in tables.

Results: Thirty-two (32) out of the 35 medical/surgical clinical specialties available at the RSUTH applied for and obtained accreditation for postgraduate medical and surgical training of the WACP, WACS, and the NPMCN. There were 16 respondents who were heads of the clinical departments, male to female ratio 1:1, and their mean age was 49.13 years. There was 100% success in membership accreditations, and 93.75% success in Fellowship accreditations of the NPMCN-Physicians. The outcome of accreditation for WACP was 100% success in membership accreditation, and 95.8% success in Fellowship accreditations. The outcome of NPMCN-Surgeons was 100% for Memberships and 100% for Fellowships, and the outcome WACS 100% for Membership and 87.5% success for Fellowships.

Conclusion: Thirty-three medical/surgical specialties underwent accreditation visits from two colleges across departments within a year in a single institution. There was 95.8% mean success rate in membership accreditations and a mean success rate 94.3% for fellowship accreditations. Sustained efforts in welfare and training matters are recommended to guarantee success in subsequent accreditations.

Introduction

The global practice of postgraduate medical training is that of mentorship and clinical tutelage under clinicians in accredited institutions [1,2] following entry examinations specifying requirements for qualification. Accreditation, apparently, a determinant of institutional “fitness” for training at any level, is a financially taxing exercise requiring the commitment of the administrators, participation of trainers, staff, learners, and the commitment of the administration. An institution is licensed or accredited for training after certain criteria are met, and the success of this accreditation exercise among others provide assurance to learners and the public on the quality standards of the training programs offered [3,4]. Although three categories of considerations: ‘structure,’ ‘process,’ and ‘outcomes - have long been proposed for accreditation of clinical training programs [5], emphasis on outcome was brought to the fore following the International Conference on Residency Education of 2013, convened by the Royal College of Physicians and Surgeons of Canada [6]. These outcome measures include learning outcomes (Board Examinations Performance and Completion Rates), patient and population health outcomes (patient’s experiences of care), and health system outcomes (impact/footprint of practice on health system).

Different countries may have different names for the accrediting bodies, however, what is certain is that statutory professional colleges recognized by law for the purpose of teaching and transfer of clinical knowledge and skills to intending trainees are responsible for screening training institutions using known criteria to determine their qualification for the exercise. Availability of physical structures and offices for training, adequacy of different levels of personnel, equipment, instruments, structured training programs, support services, commitment to adequate welfare for trainers and trainees, etc., are critically and impartially evaluated by the accrediting body. At the end of the accreditation exercise, a verdict is pronounced, which determines the scope of training or otherwise allowed in such prospecting training institution. In the Nigerian setting, the statutory bodies are: The Postgraduate Medical College of Nigeria (a national indigenous body); the West African College of Surgeons, and the West African College of Physicians – which are regional bodies. Post graduate medical training started in Nigeria in 1973 following the formation of the West African College of Surgeons [7,8] These bodies are legally backed by the Medical Residency Training Act (MRTA) of 2017 [9].

The conduct of accreditation for departmental postgraduate training programs is an expected occurrence for any department/institution that has assumed the status of a teaching hospital (for teaching/training along with service delivery and research) for prospective residents within our area of practice. The improved standards brought about by a thorough accreditation process rubs on the quality of services delivered and the quality of research output from the establishment. However, what is unusual is the number of specialties/departments that accomplish accreditation for postgraduate medical training programs within a short space of time. This study therefore aimed to evaluate and document the accreditation of specialty training programs across the Departments at the Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, focusing on the visits and outcome of visit of the accrediting colleges in the year 2024.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

A cross-sectional observational study.

Study Area

The study was carried out in Port Harcourt, the capital of Rivers State, Nigeria. The capital city is host to an international airport and a seaport, two State-owned universities, a private medical University, multinational oil and gas-exploring, oil-servicing companies, and many other tertiary, secondary and primary educational and health institutions (both private and public).

Study Settings

The Rivers State University Teaching Hospital were the setting for the study.

Study Instrument

A semi-structured self-administered questionnaire.

Study Variables

The variables of interest were socio-demographic data; postgraduate accreditation status before the year 2024; specialties/departmental participation (with dates) in accreditation of postgraduate medical programs in the year 2024; outcome of accreditation exercise of the postgraduate medical colleges in the year 2024, accreditation by other agencies within the year of study.

Study Population

The clinical Heads of Departments (HODs) of all the Departments in the Hospital were recruited for the study, as well as the Head of Media Unit of the hospital from which the official list of accredited specialties was obtained.

Sampling Method

Total population of clinical HODs was used.

Data Analysis

Data obtained was analyzed, presented in tables and graphs. Quantitative variables were expressed as percentages. A score of 1 point is awarded for full accreditation, and 0.5 for a partial accreditation. Percentage accreditation success rate for each faculty/department was arrived at by dividing the obtained score (accreditation granted) by the total score (prayers made).

Bias

None.

Reliability of Instrument

The study data was scrutinized by all the authors for authenticity or otherwise.

Research Ethics Approval

The ethical approval for this research was gotten from the Rivers State University Ethical Board. Data confidentiality was maintained.

Results

Thirty-three (33) out of the 35 medical/surgical specialties available at the Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, Port Harcourt, Nigeria applied for and obtained accreditation for postgraduate medical and surgical training of the WACP, WACS, and the NPMCN. Twenty-five (25) medical specialties from four Departments, and eight (8) surgical specialties from six (6) Departments. Two specialties from two Departments – Family Medicine, and Obstetrics & Gynaecology, were already accredited. The mean accreditation success rate across the Departments were 95.8% for Membership and 95.8% for Fellowship.

Table 1: Shows the Demographic Distribution of the Respondents

S/N	Age of the Heads of Departments – (HODs)	Status of the Respondents (HOD)	Sex of the Respondent	Accreditation in 2024
1	48	HOD	Female	Yes
2	42	HOD	Male	Yes
3	51	HOD	Male	Yes
4	48	HOD	Female	No
5	41	HOD	Male	Yes
6	53	HOD	Female	Yes
7	57	HOD	Male	Yes
8	57	HOD	Male	No
9	45	HOD	Male	Yes
10	51	HOD	Male	Yes
11	44	HOD	Female	Yes
12	45	HOD	Female	Yes
13	53	HOD	Female	Yes
14	45	HOD	Female	Yes
15	62	HOD	Male	Yes
16	44	HOD	Female	Yes
Mean Age of Respondents: 49.125 years; 8 males and 8 females				

Table 1 shows the demographic distribution of the respondents. There were 16 respondents who were heads of the clinical departments (HODs) that underwent accreditation by the West African College of Physicians (WACP), West African College of Surgeons (WACS), and the National Postgraduate Medical College of Nigeria (NPMCN) in the year 2024. There were 8 male HODs, and 8 females HODs, and their ages ranged from 41-62 years with a mean of 49.13 years. Table 2 shows the medical specialties visited by the accrediting Colleges in the year 2024. Paediatrics and

Child Health, Family Medicine, and the specialties in Internal Medicine were already accredited by the West African College of Physicians (WACP) before 2024. Sixteen specialties spread across 2 Departments of Community Medicine and Pathology applied for the accreditation of the WACP. Similarly, 24 medical specialties from the Departments of Internal Medicine, Public Health, Paediatrics and Child Health, and Pathology Departments applied for the accreditation of the National Postgraduate Medical College of Nigeria (NPMCN) within the period under study (2024).

Table 2: Medical Specialties Visited by the Accrediting Colleges

Specialty			Accrediting Institution	
			NPMCN-Date Visit	WACP-Date of Visit
Internal Medicine	1	General Internal Medicine	5 th -8 th June 2024	Already secured Accreditation before 2024
	2	Cardiology	5 th -8 th June 2024	“
	3	Gastroenterology	5 th -8 th June 2024	“
	4	Dermatology	5 th -8 th June 2024	“
	5	Geriatrics	5 th -8 th June 2024	“
	6	Nephrology	5 th -8 th June 2024	“
	7	Endocrinology	Did Not Apply	“
	8	Neurology	5 th -8 th June 2024	Did Not Apply
Public Health and Community Medicine	1	Epidemiology	7 th -9 th July 2024	25 th -26 th July 2024
	2	Biostatistics	7 th -9 th July 2024	25 th -26 th July 2024
	3	Environmental Health	7 th -9 th July 2024	25 th -26 th July 2024
	4	Health Policy, Planning and Management	7 th -9 th July 2024	25 th -26 th July 2024
	5	Health Economics	7 th -9 th July 2024	25 th -26 th July 2024
	6	Public Health Nutrition	7 th -9 th July 2024	25 th -26 th July 2024
	7	Occupational Health	7 th -9 th July 2024	25 th -26 th July 2024
	8	Family and Reproductive Health	7 th -9 th July 2024	25 th -26 th July 2024
	9	Public Health Education/Promotion	7 th -9 th July 2024	25 th -26 th July 2024
	10	Rehabilitative and Social Medicine	7 th -9 th July 2024	25 th -26 th July 2024
	11	Primary Health Care	7 th -9 th July 2024	25 th -26 th July 2024
	12	International Health	7 th -9 th July 2024	25 th -26 th July 2024
Pathology	1	Anatomical Pathology	July/October 2024	November 2024
	2	Chemical Pathology	2 nd -4 th July 2024	November 2024
	3	Medical Microbiology and Parasitology	2 nd -4 th July 2024	November 2024
	4	Hematology and Blood Transfusion Medicine	2 nd -4 th July 2024	November 2024
*Paediatrics and Child Health			20 th -23 rd April 2024	Already secured Accreditation before 2024
Family Medicine			Already secured Accreditation before 2024	Already secured Accreditation before 2024

Note: NPMCN – National Postgraduate Medical College of Nigeria. WACS – West African College of Physicians.

*Paediatrics already had full accreditation for West African College of Physicians

Table 3: Surgical Specialties Visited by the Accrediting Colleges

S/N	Specialty	Accrediting Institution	
		NPMCN-Date of Visit	WACS-Date of Visit
1	General Surgery	Did not apply for NPMCN Accreditation	19 th -20 th June 2024
2	Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery	Did not apply for NPMCN Accreditation	19 th -20 th June 2024
3	Urology	Did not apply for NPMCN Accreditation	19 th -20 th June 2024
4	Orthopaedics & Trauma	Did not apply for NPMCN Accreditation	25 th – 26 th June, 2024

5	Anaesthesiology	1 st -3 rd Aug. 2024	1 st – 3 rd Aug. 2024
6	Ophthalmology	4 th -6 th Aug. 2024	Sept. 2024
7	Otorhinolaryngology (ENT)	19 th – 21 st Dec. 2024	2 nd -5 th June 2024
8	Radiology/Radiodiagnosis	Already secured Accreditation before 2024	August 2024
9	Obstetrics and Gynecology	Already secured Accreditation before 2024	Already secured Accreditation before 2024

Note: NPMCN – National Postgraduate Medical College of Nigeria. WACS – West African College of Surgeons

Table 3 shows the surgical specialties visited by the Accrediting Colleges. Obstetrics and Gynecology had already secured the accreditation of the National Postgraduate Medical College of Nigeria (NPMCN) and the West African College of Surgeons (WACS) before 2024. Three surgical specialties (Anaesthesiology, Ophthalmology, Otorhinolaryngology (ENT), were

visited by the NPMCN, eight specialties (General Surgery, Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery, Urology, Orthopaedics & Trauma, Anaesthesiology, Ophthalmology, Otorhinolaryngology, and Radiology/Radiodiagnosis) were visited by the WACS in the year 2024.

Table 4: Outcome of Accreditation Visit by National College for Physicians (NPMCN)

Departments/Specialty			Accrediting Institution (NPMCN)		% Success
			Membership	Fellowship	
Internal Medicine	1	fGeneral Internal Medicine	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	Membership: 24÷24x100 =100% Fellowship: 22.5÷24x100 =93.75%
	2	fCardiology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	3	Gastroenterology	Full	Partial 2 Years (0.5)	
	4	Dermatology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	5	Geriatrics	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	6	Nephrology	Full	Partial 2 Years (0.5)	
	7	pNeurology	Full	Partial 2 Years (0.5)	
Public Health and Community Medicine	1	Epidemiology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	2	Biostatistics	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	3	Environmental Health	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	4	Health Policy, Planning and Management	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	5	Health Economics	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	6	Public Health Nutrition	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	7	Occupational Health	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	8	Family and Reproductive Health	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	9	Public Health Education/Promotion	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	10	Rehabilitative and Social Medicine	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	11	Primary Health Care	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	12	International Health	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
Pathology	1	Anatomical Pathology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	2	Chemical Pathology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	3	Medical Microbiology and Parasitology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	4	Haematology and Blood Transfusion Medicine	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
*Paediatrics and Child Health			Full	Full 5 Years (1)	

Note: NPMCN – National Postgraduate Medical College of Nigeria. A score of 1 point is awarded for full accreditation, and 0.5 for a partial accreditation

Table 4 shows the outcome of accreditation visit by National Postgraduate Medical College for Physicians (NPMCN). Twenty-five specialties applied for accreditation, out of which 22 were granted full accreditation, and two had partial. There was therefore, 100% success in membership accreditation,

and 93.75% success in Fellowship accreditation of the College. Public Health and Community Medicine had the highest number of specialties (12) that were accredited from a single department, followed by the Department of Internal Medicine (8).

Table 5: Outcome of Visit by West African College of Physicians (WACP)

Department/Specialty			Accrediting Institution (WACP)		% Success
			Membership	Fellowship	
Internal Medicine	1	General Medicine	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	Membership: 24÷24x100 =100% Fellowship: 23÷24 =95.8%
	2	Cardiology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	3	Gastroenterology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	4	Dermatology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	5	Geriatrics	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	6	Endocrinology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	7	Neurology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
Public Health and Community Medicine	1	Epidemiology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	2	Biostatistics	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	3	Environmental Health	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	4	Health Policy, Planning and Management	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	5	Health Economics	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	6	Public Health Nutrition	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	7	Occupational Health	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	8	Family and Reproductive Health	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	9	Public Health Education/Promotion	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	10	Rehabilitative and Social Medicine	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	11	Primary Health Care	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	12	International Health	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
Pathology	1	Anatomical Pathology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	2	Chemical Pathology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	3	Medical Microbiology and Parasitology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	4	Hematology and Blood Transfusion Medicine	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
Paediatrics and Child Health			Already secured Accreditation before 2024	Already secured Accreditation before 2024	

Note: WACP – West African College of Physicians. A score of 1 point is awarded for full accreditation, and 0.5 for a partial accreditation.

Table 5 shows the outcome of visit by West African College of Physicians (WACP). Twenty-four specialties applied for accreditation, out of which all were granted full accreditation. There was therefore, 100% success in membership accreditation, and 100% success Fellowship. Public Health and Community Medicine had the highest number of specialties (12) that were accredited from a single department, followed by the Department of Internal Medicine (8).

Table 6 shows the outcome of accreditation visit by National College for Surgeons (NPMCN). Applications

made and “prayers” were sought for membership (Part I Accreditation) for three (3) specialist areas, out of which all were granted (2 full and 1 partial). Similarly, “prayers” were made for fellowship (Part II Accreditation) for 2 specialist areas, and all were granted. Radiology had already secured the accreditation of the NPMCN before 2024. Four specialties (General Surgery, Orthopaedic and Trauma, Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery, and Urology) however, did not apply for the accreditation of the NPMCN.

Table 6: Outcome of Accreditation Visit by National College for Surgeons (NPMCN)

S/N	Specialty	Accrediting Institution (NPMCN)		% Success
		Membership	Fellowship	
1	General Surgery	Did not apply for NPMCN Accreditation	Did not apply for NPMCN Accreditation	Membership: 2.5÷3x100 =83.3%
2	Orthopaedic and Trauma	Did not apply for NPMCN Accreditation	Did not apply for NPMCN Accreditation	
3	Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery	Did not apply for NPMCN Accreditation	Did not apply for NPMCN Accreditation	Fellowship: 3÷3x100 =100%
4	Urology	Did not apply for NPMCN Accreditation	Did not apply for NPMCN Accreditation	
5	Anaesthesiology	Full (1)	Full (1)	
6	Otorhinolaryngology (ENT)	Partial (0.5)	Did Not Apply	
7	Ophthalmology	Full (1)	Full (1)	
8	Radiology	Already secured Accreditation before 2024	Already secured Accreditation before 2024	Not scored

Note: NPMCN – National Postgraduate Medical College of Nigeria. A score of 1 point is awarded for full accreditation, and 0.5 for a partial accreditation

Table 7: Outcome of Visit by West African College of Surgeons (WACS)

S/N	Specialty	Accrediting Institution (WACS)		% Success
		Membership	Fellowship	
1	General Surgery	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	Membership: 8÷8x100 =100%
2	Orthopaedic and Trauma	Full	Partial 2 Years (0.5)	
3	Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery	Full	Partial 2 Years (0.5)	
4	Urology	Full	Full-5 Years (1)	
5	Radiology (Radiodiagnosis)	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	Fellowship: 7÷8x100 =87.5%
6	Anaesthesiology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
7	Otorhinolaryngology (ENT)	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
8	Ophthalmology	Full	Full 5 Years (1)	
	Total	8/8	7/8 (6Full, 2Partial)	

Note: WACS – West African College of Surgeons. A score of 1 point is awarded for full accreditation, and 0.5 for a partial accreditation.

The outcome of accreditation visit by West African College of Surgeons (WACS) is shown in Table 7. There were 8 applications for membership (Part I Accreditation) in specialist areas (General Surgery, Orthopaedics, Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery, Radiology, Anaesthesiology, ENT, and Ophthalmology,

and similar “prayers” were made for fellowship (Part II Accreditation) in eight (8) specialist areas. Out of these, all membership prayers were granted (100%). Similarly, “prayers” were made for fellowship for 8 specialist areas, and 6 were granted full accreditation, while 2 had partial implying 87.5% success.

Table 8: Other Accreditation (None-Residency) Visits and Outcome

S/N	Type of	Accrediting Institution	
		Date of Visit	Outcome of Visit
1	House-Manship	MDCN 6 th May 2024	Training Quota increased from 64 to 94 House Officers
2	Internship Re-Accreditation in Physiotherapy	MRTBN 30 th June-1 st July 2024	Re-accreditation Granted
3	PCR Laboratory	International Accreditation by SANAS 30 th July-1 st Aug. 2024	Granted

Note: MDCN – Medical and Dental Council of Nigeria. MRTBN – Medical Rehabilitation Therapists Board of Nigeria. PCR – Polymerase Chain Reaction Laboratory. SANAS – South African National Accreditation Systems.

Table 8 show other accreditation visits which were not residency-related and their outcome. The hospital was visited by the Medical and Dental Council of Nigeria (MDCN) to accredit the hospital for the training of house officer, with upgrade of intake from previous 64 to 94 per year. There was also Internship Re-Accreditation visit by the Physiotherapy Medical Rehabilitation Therapists Board of Nigeria (MRTBN), resulting in re-accreditation. The Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) Laboratory of the hospital was also visit by the South African National Accreditation Systems (SANAS), for quality control accreditation.

Discussion

The Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, formerly called Braithwaite Memorial Specialist Hospital (BMSH), started in 1925 as nursing home/medical facility for senior civil servants [10-12], named after Eldred Curwen Braithwaite, a pioneer British doctor. It had grown to a 250-bed hospital by 2015, according to a report from a researcher chronicling the statistical analysis of HIV/AIDS awareness of mothers in antenatal clinic [13]. In July 2018 the hospital was upgraded to the status of a Teaching Hospital for teaching, research, and service delivery, by the administration of His Excellency Chief Bar Nyesom Ezenwo Wike, the then Executive Governor of Rivers State. This State-owned hospital grew in facility and manpower to a multispecialty 536-bed hospital with annexes at Maxillofacial Hospital (and the Mother & Child hospital). It was with this background that the accreditation of specialties and departments for training programs by the National Postgraduate Medical College of Nigeria (NPMCN) and West African Colleges of Surgeons and Physicians (WACS and WACP) was carried out in the hospital, akin to installation of software in an existing computer hardware. These multiple accreditation exercises were expedited under the visionary and energetic leadership of the Chief Medical Director – Prof. Chizindu Akubudike Alikor, with the full support of the Executive Governor of Rivers State - His Excellency Sir Amaopusenibo Siminalayi Fubara. This led to the outstanding achievement of mean success rate of 95.8% in membership and 94.3% in fellowship accreditations.

The choice of specialists appointed to head the Departments were partly based on the number of years of experience post fellowship, the academic ranking among peers, and willingness to energetically work to achieve set goals. The Heads who prepared the Departments and Specialties for the accreditation for both colleges were 8 males and 8 females, and their ages ranged from 41-62 years with a mean of 49.13 years. This equitable distribution of the genders in

demographic distribution speaks to improved female education in Rivers State and highlights the unique role that women just like men are playing in societal development. The implication of our finding is that the advocacy for female education [14-16], is yielding some results in Southern Nigeria. A similar finding was seen in a study among General Surgeons of the American College of Surgeons holding academic positions reported that there 168 men and 149 women, and that the gender or marital status did not affect their career performance [17]. The Heads of Departments in our study successfully prepared the thirty-two medical/surgical specialties across Departments in the hospital, and they were evaluated by training colleges in the year 2024 and had accreditations, with 24 being medical specialties and 8 surgical specialties. Two Departments (Obstetrics & Gynaecology, and Family Medicine) had earlier secured accreditation before year 2024. This number of specialty accreditations visits conducted within a single institution in one year was really remarkable.

Accreditation of specialty programs in departments have set criteria to be met for both the NPMCN and the WACS, and the final approval to grant accreditation is often done at a conference (hosted by one of the West African countries – for WACS, or in Nigeria for NPMCN). One of such cardinal requirements is availability trainers who hold fellowship positions at these colleges. More surgical specialties were visited by the WACS than by the NPMCN as seen from the 8 surgical specialties (General Surgery, Urology, Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery, Orthopaedics & Trauma, Anaesthesiology, Ophthalmology, Otorhinolaryngology, and Radiology) and 3 (Anaesthesiology, Ophthalmology, Otorhinolaryngology) by the NPMCN in the year under study. The implication of this finding is that high number of specialists in the surgical specialties had strong presence at the WACS and few at the NPMCN. This observation is further strengthened by the report from a study that the WACS in 35 years had produced 2.8 times more surgeons than their NPMCN counterpart [18]. The situation appears to be different for the medical specialties as these specialists maintained high presence in both colleges. This reasoning is strengthened by the finding that out of the 24 medical specialties that applied for and obtained the accreditation of the NPMCN, 7 were in Internal Medicine Department, 12 were in Public Health and Community Medicine, 4 in Pathology, and 1 in Pediatrics and Child Health. A relatively high number of specialties in Community Medicine has also been reported in India [17]. The accreditation visits for the West African College of Physicians were similar except

that Pediatrics and Child Health had already secured accreditation before 2024.

The out of accreditation visit can usually be: “Full Accreditation”, “Partial Accreditation”, “Not recommended for Accreditation”, “Revoked Accreditation”, etc. [19]. Hence, although applications and visitations from the accrediting colleges were important, the outcome of the accreditations was emphasized from the inception of the hospital administration with the support of the Leadership of the State, as being necessary for further development of the State. To achieve this goal, several committees were formed across departments, all consultants/lecturers were motivated and in high spirit working to actualize the set mandate. It was not surprising therefore, that the outcome of accreditation visits by National Postgraduate Medical College for Physicians (Non-Surgical Specialties) in the year 2024 was successful and impressive as all 24 specialties who applied were granted membership accreditation – 100% success rate; and 22 had full fellowship accreditations, while two specialties had partial fellowship accreditations – 93.75% success rate. A similar achievement was recorded with the Membership and Fellowship accreditations of the WACP with 100% success in Membership and 95.8% success in Fellowship accreditations. The highest number of specialties accredited from a single department for both the NPMCN and WACP was from the Public Health and Community Medicine, followed by the Department of Internal Medicine. This is rather not surprising, as the highest number of specialty visits by both colleges was also in Public Health and Community Medicine.

It has been observed earlier in a Nigerian research work, that “inadequate funding, shortage of academic staff, inadequate infrastructural facilities, brain-drain and strike actions” [20] were impediments to effective programme accreditation in tertiary institutions in Nigeria [21]. This may partly explain why 4 surgical specialties did not apply for the National College (NPMCN) accreditation. However, the outcome of the visit by NPMCN for Surgeons for Membership and Fellowship for all the three specialties that applied, was 100% success. Additionally, 100% success was recorded for Membership and 87.5% success for Fellowship accreditations of the West African College of Surgeons (WACS), and two specialties (Orthopaedic & Trauma, and Plastic & Reconstructive Surgery) had partial accreditations for Fellowship. Surmounting the above listed impediments/challenges and those reported in Africa in securing accreditation [22], the Smile Train Team has already visited the hospital in January 2025 to accredit the hospital as a center for Smile Train cleft

lip/palate surgeries; and preparations are already ongoing to secure accreditation for some surgical specialties that did not participate in 2024 accreditations in the year 2025, and these include: Pediatric Surgery, Accident & Emergency Medicine, Cardiothoracic Surgery, Neurosurgery.

Within the same study period, apart from accreditations from residency training colleges, there were other accreditations carried out in the hospital by the Medical and Dental Council of Nigeria (MDCN) to revalidate the one-year training experience for House Officers; Internship Re-Accreditation visit by the Physiotherapy Medical Rehabilitation Therapists Board of Nigeria (MRTBN); and the quality control accreditation for Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) Laboratory of the hospital by the South African National Accreditation Systems (SANAS). These accreditations were done in tandem with recommendations for the practice of physiotherapy [23], Polymerase Chain Reaction Laboratory [24], Postgraduation Internship by the MDCN (Odia & George, 2008), and they also ended in positive affirmation. These are equally important support specialties/aspects for patient care in the tertiary hospital which add value to the residency program.

Study Limitations

The limitation of this study is that it did not include the details of preparations for the accreditation, as it only focused on the visits and outcome of visit of the accrediting colleges in the year 2024. However, this study opens up another research area for another study to be carried out.

Conclusion

Thirty-two medical/surgical specialties underwent accreditation visits across departments within a year in a single institution, and there was 95.8% mean success rate in membership accreditations and a mean success rate 94.8% for fellowship accreditations. The Department of Community Medicine & Public Health, and the Internal Medicine had the highest number of specialties visited and accredited by the NPMCN and the WACP. The combined efforts of the political office holders (State Governance) - with proper allocation of resources, hospital administration, were responsible for the recorded success.

Recommendations

Further accreditations will be expected at the institution at the expiration of the partial and full accreditations achieved. Additionally, the quality of training of the residents enrolled following this massive accreditation will be judged by the outcome of their examinations at the postgraduate medical

examinations. Hence, there is need for “all hands to be on deck” in welfare and training matters, especially organization and attendance of departmental (local) and college (national) update courses to awaken the newly employed residents to the scope of required content of learning. A good synergy among the three levels of authority (State Government, Hospital Management, and the Medical/Surgical Specialists) is therefore highly recommended for achievement of success in accreditation of programs for specialist medical/surgical residency training programs.

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Conflict of Interest

None declared.

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